

Evaluation of intramuscular injection applications of nursing students

Hemşirelik öğrencilerinin intramüsküler enjeksiyon uygulamalarının değerlendirilmesi

Zeynep Doğan¹, Sermin Timur Taşhan²

¹ Öğr. Gör. SANKO Üniversitesi, Hemşirelik Bölümü, Gaziantep/ Türkiye, Zeynep.dogan@sanko.edu.tr, 0000-0002-5984-0835

² Prof. Dr. İnönü Üniversitesi, Hemşirelik Bölümü, Malatya/ Türkiye, sermin.timur@inonu.edu.tr, 0000-0003-3421-0084

ABSTRACT

The research was conducted as a descriptive study to evaluate the intramuscular injection applications of nursing students. The population of the study consisted of 110 senior year students of the Department of Nursing at Inonu University, Malatya Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Nursing, who accepted to participate in the study in the 2013-2014 Spring semester. The student identification form and the observation form developed by the researcher using in the collection of the data. Data were evaluated using percentage distribution, standard deviation, Fisher exact test, Chi square test, Mann Whitney U test and Independent T test. During the undergraduate educations of students, the injection application average was 26.10 ± 7.32 and the injection application average alone was 10.48 ± 10.53. It was determined that one of every three students did not apply IM injection with the instructor who gave the lesson. All of the students preferred the dorsogluteal region during IM injection and more than half of them used deep breathing as a pain relief method. It has been found that all of the students in the study have applied IM injection to dorsogluteal region which is not highly preferred and they did not use pain relief methods in sufficient numbers and through the teaching staff and practice experience and training as the number of IM injections applied increased, the technical skills increased.

Key Words:

Nursing, Nursing Students, Intramuscular Injection, Pain Reduction Methods

Corresponding Author/Sorumlu Yazar:

Öğr. Gör. SANKO Üniversitesi, Hemşirelik Bölümü, Gaziantep/ Türkiye, Zeynep.dogan@sanko.edu.tr, 0000-0002-5984-0835

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.11071395

Received Date/Gönderme Tarihi:

10.01.2024

Accepted Date/Kabul Tarihi:

28.03.2024

Published Online/Yayımlanma Tarihi

31.03.2024

Öz

Araştırma hemşirelik öğrencilerinin intramüsküler (İM) enjeksiyon uygulamalarının değerlendirilmesi amacıyla tanımlayıcı olarak yapılmıştır. Araştırmanın evrenini İnönü Üniversitesi Malatya Sağlık Bilimleri Fakültesi Hemşirelik bölümü 2013-2014 Bahar döneminde öğrenim gören araştırmayı kabul eden 110 Hemşirelik bölümü son sınıf öğrencisi oluşturmuştur. Verilerin toplanmasında araştırmacı tarafından geliştirilen Öğrenci Tanıtım Formu ve Gözlem Formu kullanılmıştır. Veriler, yüzdeler dağılımı, standart sapma, Fisher exact testi, ki-kare testi, mann-whitney U testi ve independent t testi kullanılarak değerlendirilmiştir. Öğrencilerin lisans eğitimi boyunca enjeksiyon uygulama ortalaması 26.10 ± 7.32 ve tek başına enjeksiyon uygulama ortalaması 10.48 ± 10.53 bulunmuştur. Her 3 öğrenciden birinin dersi veren öğretim elemanı ile İM enjeksiyon uygulamadığı saptanmıştır. Öğrencilerin hepsinin İM enjeksiyon uygulaması sırasında dorsolateral bölgeyi tercih ettiği ve yarıdan fazlasının ağrıyı azaltma yöntemi olarak derin nefes alıp verme yöntemini kullandığı saptanmıştır. Araştırmada öğrencilerin tamamının İM enjeksiyonu çok fazla tercih edilmesi istenmeyen dorsolateral bölgeye uyguladıkları, ağrıyı azaltma yöntemlerini yeterli sayıda kullanmadıkları, öğretim elemanı ile uygulama deneyimi ve eğitimleri boyunca uyguladıkları İM enjeksiyon sayısı arttıkça teknik becerilerinin arttığı saptanmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Hemşirelik, Hemşirelik Öğrencileri, İntramüsküler Enjeksiyon, Ağrıyı Azaltma Yöntemleri

INTRODUCTION

In all the institutions providing health care services, it is one of the primary responsibilities of nurses to ensure that oral and parenteral drugs are used safely and properly. Administering drugs, administered in accordance with the request of physicians, in accordance with the eight rights of medication, as well as following up the individuals and assessing them comprehensively in terms of the side effects of drug after the application are among the primary duties of nurses (Kuzu, 1999). The intramuscular injection (IM) application, an important part of drug administration, is a common nursing intervention (Perry and Potter, 2011; Güneş et al. 2009). IM injection is to administer drug into the muscle tissue by passing through the subcutaneous tissue (Perry and Potter 2011; McWilliam, Botwinski and LaCourse, 2014; Nicoll and Hesby 2002; Çakırcalı 2000; Sabuncu 2002).

Reference | Atf : Doğan, Z. & Timur Taşhan, S. (2024). Evaluation of intramuscular injection applications of nursing students. Journal of 5N1Quality, 2(1), 8-16

IM injection is not a simple application and it is a complex application requiring technical skills and some decisions about the application method and the tools used for it (Hunter, 2008; Gneř et al. 2009) In case that IM injection is not applied carefully and the correct injection technique is not applied, it may cause severe complications (Nicoll and Hesby, 2002; Small, 2004; Floyd and Meyer 2007). It has been stated that the complications occurring during IM injection depend on the duration of drug administration, amount of the drug administered, rotation among the drug administration regions, not paying attention to the aseptic technique in the drug administration region, and not using the proper technique during the injection (Mitchell and Whitney, 2001).

The unwanted situations that may occur in the region after injection such as pain, rigidity, sensitivity, and rash cause patients to have physical and psychological disturbance and make compliance to treatment difficult (Hunter, 2008). At this point, it has been stated in the literature that using air-lock technique and Z-track technique, distraction, applying rotation among the regions, drug administration rate, cold application on the injection site, deep breathing and massaging are important to prevent the pain development in IM injection site (Small, 2004; Gneř et al., 2009; Kara, 2013).

The complications developing, mainly IM based pain, are the complications that can be prevented significantly when nurses have adequate knowledge and skills. In preventing these complications, it is significant that the nursing students improve their intramuscular injection skills before entering the profession.

Aim

The study was conducted in order to assess the IM injection applications of the nursing students.

METHODS

Type of Study

This is a descriptive study.

Place and Date of the Study

The study was conducted in Family Health Center, which is located in Malatya city and where Public Health Nursing course was performed, between February 2014 and August 2014.

Population and The Sample of The Study

The population of the study was composed of 114 fourth-year students studying in Nursing Department of Inonu University Malatya Faculty of Health Sciences in 2013-2014 spring term. The whole population was included in the study. 4 students rejected to participate in the research and the study was completed with 110 students.

The Data Collection Tools

“Student Information Form” and “Observation Form” were used in data collection. The student information form was developed by the researcher and it consists of a total of 13 questions. The observation form is a 20-item form used to observe the intramuscular injection application steps.

The Application of Data Collection Tools

The data of the study were collected between February and May 2014 using the interview and observation methods. The student information form was filled out by the students and the observation form was filled out by the researcher.

Data Assessment

In the assessment of the data, SPSS 17.0 packaged software was used in the computer environment. Percentage distribution, standard deviation, fisher exact test, chi-square test, Mann-Whitney U test, and independent t test reliability analysis test were used in the statistical assessment.

Ethical Considerations

Before starting the study, the required permissions were received from Inonu University Malatya Faculty of Health Sciences and Malatya Clinical Trials Ethics Committee. The students were informed about the study and their written consents were received.

FINDINGS

Distribution Of The Socio-Demographic Characteristics Of The Students

In the study, it was determined that the age average of the students was 23.12 ± 2.25 , 51.8% of them were aged 23 and over, 61.8% were female, and 90% had high school graduation (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of the Socio-demographic characteristics of the Students

Socio-Demographic Characteristics (S=110)	S	%
*Age		
23<	53	48.2
23≥	57	51.8
Gender		
Female	68	61.8
Male	42	38.2
Education Status		
High School	99	90.0
Health Vocational High School	11	10.0

Distribution Of The Experiences Of The Students With IM Injection.

It was found that 70% of the students stated that they performed the first IM injection application in the first year of university. In the study, 30.9% of the students stated that they applied IM injection for 11-20 times during their undergraduate education. In addition, 30% of the students stated that they did not apply IM injection with the instructor of the course. And 85.5% of the students stated that they experienced the IM injection application alone. 52.2% of the students who applied IM injection alone stated that they applied IM injection for 1-10 times (Table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of the Experiences of the Students with IM Injection

Intramuscular Injection Experience	S	%
First IM Injection Application Class		
Practicing in First Class	77	70.0
Practicing in Second Class	26	23.6
Applying in Three and Fourth Class	7	6.4
* Number of IM Injection Applications		
5-10	25	22.7
11-20	34	30.9
21-30	26	23.7
31 and over	25	22.7
Number of IM Injection Practices with Instructo		
Never Doing	33	30.0
1-10	72	65.5
11- and over	5	4.5
Alone IM Injection Application Experience		
Yes	94	85.5
No	16	14.5
** Number of IM Injection Applications Alone (s= 94)		
1-10	49	52.2
11-20	28	29.8
21 and over	17	18.0

Distribution Of Application Techniques Of The Students For The IM Injection And Their Pain Relief Applications

In the study, it was determined that all the students selected the proper needle and 90.9% of them prepared the drug properly. 68.2% of the students did not change injector needle before injection, 94.5% had the individuals have the proper position during injection, and 81.8% determined the proper site for injection. 59.1% of the students did not wait for the injection site to dry after they wiped it with alcohol cotton, and 53.6% paid attention to aseptic techniques during injection application. 93.6% of the students stretched the injection site during IM injection, 84.5% applied the right entry angle to the tissue, 91.8% made aspiration before administering the drug to the tissue, and 71.8% did not move the injector during the injection and all of the students made compression on the injection site using dry cotton after the injection. Our other finding not included in the questionnaire was that the whole of the registration after the intramuscular injection was made by the working nursing (Table 3).

In the study, it was determined that 57.3% of the students told to the patients to take a deep breath and 93.6% did not use the air-lock technique during the application. Another result not included in the Table was that we determined that the students did not use the other pain relief techniques such

as Z technique, distraction, applying local ice on the injection location after the injection, massage and mechano-analgesia techniques during IM injection were not used (Table 3).

Table 3. Distribution Of Application Techniques Of The Students For The IM Injection And Their Pain Relief Applications

	Yes		No	
	S	%	S	%
Application Technique for Intramuscular Injection				
Selecting the proper needle	110	100.0	-	-
Preparing the drug properly	100	90.9	10	9.1
Changing the injector needle before injection	35	31.8	75	68.2
Having the individual take the proper position	104	94.5	6	5.5
*Determining the proper site for injection	90	81.8	20	18.2
Wiping the injection site with alcohol and then waiting to dry	45	40.9	65	59.1
Paying attention to the aseptic technique during the procedure	59	53.6	51	46.4
Stretching the site	103	93.6	7	6.4
Inserting the injector into the tissue with the angle of 90°	93	84.5	17	15.5
Performing aspiration procedure before administering the drug	101	91.8	9	8.2
Not moving the injector during injection	79	71.8	31	27.9
Applying pressure to the injection site with a dry cotton after the injection	110	100	-	-
Pain Relief Applications				
Saying the patients to take a deep breath during the injection	63	57.3	47	42.7
Using the air-lock technique during the injection	7	6.4	103	93.6

Comparison Of The IM Injection Technique And The Number Of IM Injection Performed By The Students

The number of IM injection applied by the students who determined the location properly during IM injection was 27.6?18.2 and the number of IM injection applied by the students who did not determine the location properly was 18.9?9.86. The difference between them was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

In the study, no statistically significant difference was determined between other steps of IM injection technique and the number of IM injection ($p > 0.05$) (Table 4).

Table 4. Comparison Of The IM Injection Technique And The Number Of IM Injection Performed By The Students

Application Technique for Intramuscular Injection	injection Application number of $\bar{X} \pm SS$	* Statistical Test and Significance
Selecting The Proper Needle		
Yes	26.1 \pm 17.3	
No	-	
Preparing The Drug Properly		
Yes	26.4 \pm 17.8	U= 486.00
No	23.0 \pm 10.5	p= 0.884

Changing The Injector Needle Before Injection		
Yes	26.5 _± 15.9	t= 0.171
No	25.9 _± 18.0	p= 0.866
Having the individual take the proper position		
Yes	26.7 _± 17.4	U= 171.00
No	15.0 _± 8.94	p= 0.101
Determining The Proper Site For Injection		
Yes	27.6 _± 18.2	U=635.00
No	18.9 _± 9.86	p= 0.030
Wiping The Injection Site With Alcohol And Then Waiting To Dry		
Yes	27.4 _± 18.5	t= 0.664
No	25.1 _± 16.5	p= 0.504
Paying Attention To The Aseptic Technique During The Procedure		
Yes	27.5 _± 18.7	t= 0.921
No	24.4 _± 15.4	p= 0.356
Stretching The Site		
Yes	26.7 _± 17.5	U= 212.5
No	16.7 _± 11.1	p= 0.062
Inserting The Injector Into The Tissue With The Angle Of 90°		
Yes	26.7 _± 17.9	U=698.0
No	22.3 _± 13.0	p= 0.445
Performing Aspiration Procedure Before Administering The Drug		
Yes	26.1 _± 17.6	U=432.00
No	25.5 _± 13.3	p= 0.732
Not Moving The Injector During Injection		
Yes	27.7 _± 17.5	t= 1.621
No	21.8 _± 16.1	p= 0.106
Applying pressure to the injection site with a dry cotton after the injection		
Yes	26.1 _± 17.3	
No	-	

Comparison Of The Pain Relief Applications Performed By The Students During IM Injection And Their Number Of IM Injection

While the number of the applications of the students who told patients to take a deep breath during IM injection was 30.0_±19.9, the number of applications by the students who did not tell them to take a deep breath was 20.7_±11.1. The difference between them was found to be statistically significant (p<0.05) (Table 5).

The number of the injection of the students who used the air-lock technique during IM injection was 34.0_±24.6 and the number of the injection of those who did not use this technique was 25.5_±16.7. The difference between them was not statistically significant (p<0.05) (Table 5).

Table 5. Comparison Of The Pain Relief Applications Performed By The Students During IM Injection And Their Number Of IM Injection

Pain Relief Applications	injection Application number of X _± SS	*Statistical Test and Significance
Saying The Patients To Take A Deep Breath During The Injection		
Yes	30.0±19.9	t= 2.88
No	20.7±11.1	p= 0.05
Using The Air-Lock Technique During The Injection		
Yes	34.0±24.6	U=294.0
No	25.5±16.7	p=0.41

DISCUSSION

In the study, it was determined that most of the students applied IM injection for the first time in their first year (Table 2). It was a pleasing finding that most of the nursing students applied the intramuscular injection for the first time in their first year in terms of professionalization and improving the basic skills.

In the present study, the mean number of IM injections during the students' education was determined to be 26.10±17.32 (Table 2). In the study by Alan, it was determined that the mean value of IM injections by the nursing students based on the locations was 12.77±15.36 to Dorsogluteal site, 3.49 ± 5.98 to Ventrogluteal site, 2.60±5.99 to Vastus Lateralis muscle, 1.58 ±3.67 to Rectus Femoris muscle, and 5.50±10.21 to deltoid muscle, respectively (Alan, 2015). It was considered that the difference between the result of the Alan's study and the result of the present study was caused by the fact that the total number of the IM injections was taken into consideration in the present study ignoring the injection site; whereas, the number of the applications was evaluated based on the injection site in the study of Alan.

In the study, it was determined that most of the students applied IM injection with the instructor of the course (Table 2). The fact that most of the students had experience of IM injection with the instructor of the course may be considered to be positive but the desired situation is that all the students had the experience to apply IM injection with the instructor. It was considered that the reason for not being able to make that happen was that there were a great number of students and limited number of instructors.

In the study, it was determined that all of the nursing students selected the proper injector (Table 3). In the literature, there is limited number of observation and assessment of the applications by the students, it has been determined in the assessments based on knowledge that the students do not know the length of the needle (Altıok et al., 2007; Güneş et al., 2009; Sağkal et al., 2014; Alan, 2015). In the study by Alan, it was determined that 90.6% of the students did not know the right needle length (Alan, 2015). But it was considered the difference between the result of Alan and the result of the present study

was caused by the fact that the present study was based on observation and Alan's study was based on knowledge. It was also considered that the selection of the students were mostly right as the students had limited number of injectors to select.

In the present study, it was determined that less than half of the nursing students did not change the injection needle before the IM injection application (Table 3). In the study by Gneř et al., it was reported that 65.5% of the nurses did not change injection needle in IM injection (Gneř et al., 2009). In the study by Sađkal et al., it was determined that 77.9% of the nursing students stated that the injection needle should be changed after absorbing drug from ampoule or vial (Sađkal et al., 2014). While the result of the present study has similarity with the result of Gneř et al., it is different from the result of Sađkal et al.,. It was thought that this difference was caused by the difference in the design of the present study and its results.

At the end of the study, it was observed that almost all of the students provided a position proper for the individual during the injection (Table 3). In the study by Sađkal et al., it was determined that 60.4% of the students did not know to provide a proper position for IM injection (Sađkal et al., 2014). The result of the present study is in parallel with the result of that study. The difference was thought to be associated with the difference in the research designs.

The rate of the nursing students preferring dorsogluteal site for IM injection was 81.2% in the study by Sađkal et al., 85.9% in the study by Glnar et al., 60% in the study by Gneř et al., and 81.8% in the study by Alan (Alan, 2015; Gneř et al., 2009; Glnar and alıřkan, 2014; Sađkal et al., 2014). As a result of the study, it was determined that all of the nursing students used dorsogluteal site for IM injection (Table 3). The study findings in the literature have a similarity with findings of the present study. The nursing students use dorsogluteal site as VG site has small anatomic structure and the determination of the site is difficult, the dorsogluteal site is a common application location and the nurses underuse the ventrogluteal site and therefore the nursing students cannot observe enough (Engstrom et al., 2000). It was observed that most of the students participating in the study determined the DG site correctly for the IM injection (Table 3).

In the present study, it was observed that half of the nursing students paid attention to the aseptic technique. However, the students did not wait to dry after wiping with alcohol (Table 3). In the study by Gktař; it was observed that 94.1% of the nurses wiped the drug administration site with antiseptic solution but they applied injection without waiting for it to dry completely (Gktař, 2014). The result of the study has similarity with the result of Gktař's study. It was considered that the nursing students may skip this step as they were in an effort of doing the application correctly by the qualification of their education.

In the present study, it was determined that the students with higher numbers of IM injection made a significant difference in the determination of the proper site, which is one of the most difficult injection technique steps of IM and the students who applied more injections made the site determination more correctly (Table 4). The result of the present study indicated that the application had an important place in converting the theory to practice.

CONCLUSION

Consequently, it was determined that most of the students applied their first IM injection in the first year, the mean number of IM injection during the undergraduate education was 26.10 ± 17.32 , less than half of the students did not apply IM injection with the instructor of the course, all of the students applied IM injection on the Dorsogluteal Site, most of the students told to the patients to take a deep breath as a method to reduce pain in the IM injection, and the students with more IM injections determined the injection site more correctly.

In accordance with these results, it may be recommended that the up-to-date information and applications on the IM injection are taught to the students in the basic nursing education, there is an obligation of each of for each student to apply a certain number of IM injections, each of the students make IM injection at least one time in every injection location under supervision of the instructor, and it is emphasized in the courses within the scope of the nursing education that ventrogluteal site is a safer site compared to dorsogluteal site for IM injection and it should be applied as the first option.

REFERENCES

- Alan, S. (2015). Determination of knowledge levels of senior nursing students regarding intramuscular injection [Master's thesis, Gazi University]. National Dissertation Center. <https://tez.yok.gov.tr/UlusalTezMerkezi/tezSorguSonucYeni.jsp>
- Altıok, M., Kuyurtar, F., Gökçe, H., and Taşdelen, B. (2007). Primary care midwives and nurses' knowledge about intramuscular injections. *Fırat University Medical Journal of Health Sciences*, 2(4), 69-84. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/237694552_Birinci_Basamak_Saglik_Hizmetinde_Calisan_Ebe_ve_Hemsirelerin_Intramuskuler_Enjeksiyonuna_Yonelik_Bilgileri
- Göktaş, N. (2014). Evaluation of intramuscular and intravenous drug applications of the nurses [Master's thesis, Erciyes University]. National Dissertation Center. <https://tez.yok.gov.tr/UlusalTezMerkezi/tezSorguSonucYeni.jsp>
- Engstrom, J.L., Giglio, N.N., Takacs, S.M., Ellis, M.C., & Cherwenka, D.I. (2000). Procedures used to prepare and administer intramuscular injections: a study of infertility nurses. *Journal of obstetric, gynecologic, and neonatal nursing: JOGNN*, 29(2), 159-68. DOI: 10.1111/j.1552-6909.2000.tb02036.x
- Floyd, S., & Meyer, A. (2007). Intramuscular injections--what's best practice. *Nursing New Zealand (Wellington, N.Z.: 1995)*, 13(6), 20-22. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17695184/>
- Gülınar, E., and Çalışkan, N. (2014). Determination of knowledge level of nurses regarding intramuscular injection administration to ventrogluteal site introduction. *Journal of Dokuz Eylül University School of Nursing*, 7(2),70-77. https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/deuhfed/issue/46808/586997#article_cite
- Güneş, Ü. Y., Zaybak, A., Biçici, B., and Çevik, K. (2009). Investigation of Nurses' Practices Towards Intramuscular Injection Procedure. *Anatolian Journal of Nursing and Health Sciences*, 12(4), 84-90. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/ataunihem/issue/2647/34054>
- Hunter, J. (2008). Intramuscular injection techniques. *Nursing standard (Royal College of Nursing (Great Britain): 1987)*, 22(24), 35-40. DOI: 10.7748/ns2008.02.22.24.35.c6413
- Kara, D. (2013). The methods for reducing pain due to intramuscular injection. *Gümüşhane University Journal of Health Sciences*, 2(2), 275-289. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/gumussagbil/issue/7504/98928>
- Kuzu, N. (1999). Subcutaneous Heparin injections: How to prevent the occurrence of pain, echymosis and heamotoma? *journal of Cumhuriyet university school of nursing*, 3(2), 40-46. <https://silo.tips/download/subktan-heparn-enjeksiyonu-ekimoz-hematome-ar-geliimi-nasl-nlenir>
- McWilliam, P. L., Botwinski, C. A., & LaCourse, J. R. (2014). Deltoid intramuscular injections and obesity. *MedSurg Nursing*, 23(1), 4-7. <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A360608998/AONE?u=anon~feb535ad&sid=googleScholar&xid=c9c71fa5>
- Mitchell, J.R., & Whitney, F.W. (2001). The effect of injection speed on the perception of intramuscular injection pain. A clinical update. *AAOHN journal : official journal of the American Association of Occupational Health Nurses*, 49(6), 286-292. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11760527/>
- Nicoll, L.H., & Hesby, A. (2002). Intramuscular injection: an integrative research review and guideline for evidence-based practice. *Applied nursing research: ANR*, 15(3), 149-62. DOI: 10.1053/apnr.2002.34142
- Perry, A.G. and Potter, P.A. (2011). *Clinical Practice Skills and Methods*. Adana: Nobel Bookstore.
- Sağkal, T., Edeer, G., Özdemir, C., Meltem, Ö., Uyanık, M. (2014). Nursing students' Knowledge about intramuscular injection. *Journal of Anatolia Nursing and Health Sciences*, 17(2), 80-89. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/ataunihem/issue/2665/34545>
- Small, S.P. (2004). Preventing sciatic nerve injury from intramuscular injections: literature review. *Journal of advanced nursing*, 47(3), 287-96. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2648.2004.03092.x.